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RIGHT TO WATER: A CASE FOR THE COLLATERAL HUMAN RIGHTS OBLIGATIONS OF BUSINESS?

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This paper discusses whether, and if yes, what obligations business actors have in respect of the right to water. It analyses the rationale for and the varying scope of such obligations based on the social function of business actors and/ or their capacity to infringe on the right to water of individuals and whole communities, including through pollution and excessive exploitation of water resources. The paper also outlines how the general corporate sustainability due diligence obligations, as recently adopted at European Union (hereafter “EU”) level, operationalise concrete substantive duties relating to the right to water. While questioning some conventional wisdom of the mainstream human rights doctrine, the paper develops from fundamental principles of law a line of interpreting extant instruments as acknowledging direct obligations of business attached to the right to water. This has direct implications for the manner in which corporate due diligence obligations should be implemented and enforced.

I. Introduction

The recognition of the right to water is a fairly recent development. Neither United Nations (*hereafter “UN”*) core human rights instruments, nor European Convention on Human Rights (*hereafter “ECHR”*) expressly refer to that right.¹ The deepening global problem of water scarcity and pollution accelerated the understanding that access to safe and sufficient water is central to the realization of other human rights, notably the right to life, health, food

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¹ However, the right features i.a. the 1949 Geneva Convention relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War (Art. 20, 26, 29 and 46) and the 1979 Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women, Art. 14(2)(h).

and personal integrity.² Protection of the right to water under international, regional and domestic human rights instruments has normative implications for the conduct of all social actors. This paper focuses on corporate actors in view of their special relationship to and position in society.³ Its central argument is that the recognition of the right to water inevitably implies certain collateral obligations for economic actors, be it in their capacity as administrators of water supply or major water “consumers” and/ or polluters.⁴ The argument is based on two underlying premises: Firstly, the legal construction of a *right* enjoyed by an individual or a collective (e.g. indigenous peoples) presupposes concomitantly a responsible duty bearer. The state-centric human rights scholarship and practice⁵ have long obscured the understanding that such a duty bearer should be established based on its power and capacity to violate that right⁶ rather than its public versus private character and/ or ownership structure. This argument will be further developed under the following section. Secondly, conceiving of States as the “primary” duty bearers under national and international law implies that there are others (“secondary”) subjects responsible for the respect and promotion of human rights, including the right to water.⁷ Corporate actors have a special role to play in view of the power and influence that these entities might (and tend to) have on the enjoyment of the right to water.

The following analysis proceeds in four parts: Section II explains the rationale for corporate human rights obligations, including how general arguments to that effect are reinforced by the special character of water as an essential common good. Section III specifies substantive human rights obligation of business pertaining to the right to water. Section IV briefly discusses

² The 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child (Arts. 24(2)(c), 27(3)); the 2006 Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (Art. 28(2)(a)); Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (hereafter “CESCR”), ‘General Comment No 15 (2002) on The Right to Water, UN Document E/C.12/2002/11; See also e.g. Joint statement of 5 UN Treaty bodies (Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women; Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights; Committee on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of their Families; Committee on the Rights of the Child; and Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities) on human rights and climate change (14 May 2020, HRI/2019/1) recognizes that climate change poses significant risks to the enjoyment of human rights protected by the respective covenants, including the right to water (paragraph 3).

³ S. Deva, *Regulating Corporate Human Rights Violations. Humanizing Business*, London and New York, Routledge, 2012, p. 14.

⁴ While agriculture alone accounts for about 70% of freshwater use globally, industry remains larger water consumer (19%) than households (12%). UN HRC, Human rights and the global water crisis: water pollution, water scarcity and water-related disasters. Report of the Special Rapporteur on the issue of human rights obligations relating to the enjoyment of a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment, January 19, 2021, A/HRC/46/28, paragraph 15.

⁵ E.g. F. Wettstein, *Business and Human Rights. Ethical, Legal and Managerial Perspectives*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2022, p. 364; W. Vandenhoele, “Transnational human rights obligations as vehicles for global justice” in: S. Adelman, A. Paliwala (eds), *Beyond Law and Development: Resistance, Empowerment and Social Injustice*, Oxon and Ney York, Routledge, 2022, p. 141.

⁶ S. Deva, *supra* note 3, p. 148. D. Bilchitz, *Fundamental Rights and the Legal Obligations of Business*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2022, p. 256.

⁷ E.g. UN HRC, The human rights to safe drinking water and sanitation, 31 October 2023, A/C.3/78/L.47, p. 2; HRC Resolution 26/9 of 14 July 2014: Elaboration of an international legally binding instrument on transnational corporations and other business enterprises with respect to human rights, p. 2.

implementing such obligations through due diligence laws, based on the example of the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (*hereafter* “CSDDD”).⁸ Section V concludes.

II. The *raison d’être* of corporate obligations in respect of the right to water

A. THE GENERAL FOUNDATIONS OF CORPORATE HUMAN RIGHTS OBLIGATIONS

The question whether private business actors have (or should have) direct and enforceable human rights obligations is by no means new. The issue remains controversial, which is well demonstrated by now over a fifty-year-record of regulatory attempts at the UN)level.⁹ Some breakthrough has been achieved with the unanimous adoption of the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (*hereafter* “UNGPs”) by the Human Rights Council in 2011.¹⁰ The UNGPs acknowledge that all business actors have an individual responsibility to respect human rights, albeit conceive such responsibility merely in terms of an expected standard of conduct rather than a legal obligation.¹¹ The efforts to directly regulate businesses through a legally binding instrument were taken up again in 2014¹², with more than a ten-year negotiation process not promising to bring a breakthrough in the near future.¹³ So where do we stand with the current foundations of the human rights obligations of business?

International human rights law (*hereafter* “IHL”) doctrine and practice have long advanced an ‘indirect’ approach to imposing and enforcing human rights obligations for business actors. It basically maintains that, alongside their duties to respect and promote human rights, States must also ensure through regulatory, administrative and judicial measures that all natural and legal persons operating within their jurisdictions respect the rights of others.¹⁴ This approach is in line with the classical doctrine founded on the idea of human rights as guarantees against the arbitrary power of state or public authorities (vertical application). Concomitantly, instan-

⁸ Directive (EU) 2024/1760 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on corporate sustainability due diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 and Regulation (EU) 2023/2859 (OJ L, 2024/1760).

⁹ For accounts of such attempts as of 1970s, see K.P. Sauvant, “The Negotiations of the United Nations Code of Conduct on Transnational Corporations: Experience and Lessons Learned”, *16 Journal of World Investment and Trade*, 2015, p. 11, at p. 87; L.C. Backer, “Multinational Corporations, Transnational Law: The United Nation’s Norms on the Responsibilities of Transnational Corporations as Harbinger of Corporate Responsibility in International Law”, *37 Columbia Human Rights Law Review*, 2005, p. 101, at p. 111.

¹⁰ UN HRC resolution 17/4 of 16 June 2011.

¹¹ UNGPs, Commentary to Guiding Principle 11. Critically e.g. S. Deva, “Treating human rights lightly: a critique of the consensus rhetoric and the language employed by the Guiding Principles”, in: S. Deva and D. Bilchitz, *Human Rights Obligations of Business*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2013, p. 73; D. Chirwa and N. Amodu, “Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Sustainable Development Goals, and Duties of Corporations: Rejecting the False Dichotomies”, *6 Business and Human Rights Journal*, 2021, p. 21, at p. 31.

¹² UN HRC Resolution 26/9 of 14 July 2014, *supra* note 7.

¹³ For the ten-year mandate of the open-ended intergovernmental working group on transnational corporations and other business enterprises with respect to human rights (*hereafter* “OEIGWG”), see <<https://www.ohchr.org/en/hr-bodies/hrc/wg-trans-corp/session10>> last accessed 6 April 2025.

¹⁴ Cf. e.g. CESCR, ‘General Comment No 15, *supra* note 2, para 1; S. Deva, *supra* note 3, p. 7. Critically on that approach D. Bilchitz, *supra* note 6, p. 64 *et seq.*

ces where individual rights and freedoms set limits to private parties' autonomy (horizontal application) under the law are numerous and involve, amongst others, cases where private actors: i) fulfil state functions (typically through outsourcing and privatization of essential services)¹⁵, create public spaces (e.g. parks, shopping malls, airport terminals)¹⁶ and iii) operate in particular hierarchy and/ or power asymmetry constellations.¹⁷ Such instances of horizontal application are invoked under international and EU human rights instruments¹⁸, as well as national constitutions.¹⁹ As these instruments normally do not name business actors as duty bearers,²⁰ most prominent role in establishing horizontal effect is played by the courts. Not surprisingly, given that practically all human rights may have implications and be invoked by private parties of a legal dispute,²¹ including by businesses themselves.²²

In essence, the state duty to protect human rights under IHRL²³ entails at best indirect obligations for corporations and relies on States for implementing and enforcing such obligations through appropriate measures.²⁴ Also national constitutional law and jurisprudence show more fondness for indirect horizontal effect, with the reach of human rights into the private

¹⁵ Ch. Unseld, "Horizontal Application", *Max Planck Encyclopedia of Comparative Constitutional Law*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2017, paragraph 11.

¹⁶ Unseld, *supra* note 15; e.g. *Evans v. Newton*, 382 U.S. 296 (1966).

¹⁷ E.g. ECtHR, *Chowdury and others/Greece* judgment of 30 March 2017 (appl. no. 21884/15) or *Jurčić/Croatia* judgment of 4 February 2021 (appl. no. 54711/15) (concerning labour relations); *López Ostra/Spain* judgment of 9 December 1994 (appl. no. 16798/90) or *Apanasewicz/Poland* judgment of 3 May 2011 (appl. no. 6854/07) (concerning adverse impacts of a factory on individual rights); CJ, judgment of 16 April 2015, *Nemzeti Fogyasztóvédelmi Hatóság v UPC Magyarország kft*, C-388/13, EU:C:2015:225 (concerning consumer protection).

¹⁸ E.g. Articles 3-5 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights of 2000, OJ C 364/1 prohibiting slavery and forced labour, medical practices infringing on personal integrity and inhuman or degrading treatment. The Court of Justice of the EU applies European fundamental rights if possible directly to relations between individuals. C.D. Classen, "L'encadrement des puissances privées au nom des droits de l'homme en droit allemand", J. Andriant-simbazovina (ed.), *Puissances privées et droits de l'Homme. Essai d'analyse juridique*, Mare Martin, coll. "Horizons européens", 2024, p. 263, at p. 268.

¹⁹ Direct horizontal effect is established in the constitutions of South Africa (Section 8(2)) and Colombia ('tutela' action under art. 86). D. Bilchitz, *supra* note 6, p. 197 *et seq.*

²⁰ Therefore, with the exception of the Common Article 3 of the 1949 Geneva Conventions, the applicability of International Humanitarian Law to non-state actors remains controversial. Such applicability is advanced by Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (hereafter "OHCHR"), "Business, human rights and conflict-affected regions: towards heightened action. Report of the Working Group on the "Issue of human rights and transnational corporations and other business enterprises: Note by the Secretary-General", July 21, 2020, p. 4. Also violations of peremptory norms (jus cogens) of IHRL are said to directly engage the legal responsibility of collective non-state actors. A. Clapham, "Human Rights obligations of non-state actors in conflict situations," *International Review of the Red Cross* 88, 2006, p. 491, at p. 523. For corporate criminal liability, see also A. Clapham, "Human Rights Obligations for Non-State-Actors: Where are We Now?", 2017, p. 1, at p. 12-15, available at SSRN: <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=2641390>> last accessed 6 April 2025. .

²¹ Unseld, *supra* note 15, para 3.

²² E.g. *First National Bank of SA Limited t/a Wesbank v Commissioner for the South African Revenue Services and Another*; (CCT19/01) [2002] ZACC 5; 2002 (4) SA 768; 2002 (7) BCLR 702 (16 May 2002).

²³ The IHRL doctrine and practice adopted classification of state obligations into duties to respect, protect and fulfil, introduced by Asbjørn Eide, Final Report on the Right to Adequate Food as a Human Right', UN Doc E/CN.4/Sub.2/1987/23, paragraphs 170-181.

²⁴ Cf. M. Krajewski, "Mandatory Human Rights Due Diligence Laws: Blurring the Lines between State Duty to Protect and Corporate Duty to Respect?" *Nordic Journal of Human Rights*, 2023, p. 1, at p. 6.

sphere and relations being said to be mediated through private (mainly civil) law.²⁵ A question arises what happens if the national legislator fails to meet its part of the duty to protect and adopt respective legislation. Is it then to be assumed that business actors are not subject to any human rights obligations?

A counterargument would maintain that international human rights obligations of business are not predicated on the adoption or not of statutory law in national jurisdictions. Surely, the existence of such laws substantially facilitates enforcement in respective jurisdictions.²⁶ Conversely, the absence of such laws neither precludes business actors from being bound by human rights, nor is it conclusive as to whether or not concrete obligations can be effectively attributed to them under particular circumstances of a case. The argument holds irrespective of a national law's systemic relationship (monist or dualist) to international law. A legislative body is but one state organ responsible for the fulfillment of state's human rights obligations, with the courts having special duty and capacity to protect when applying the law.²⁷ Where the judiciary fulfils state duty to protect despite the absence of implementing relevant domestic legislation, it gives direct horizontal effect to international human rights norms.

Postulating direct human rights obligations for business requires justification. The rationale for burdening an entity with human rights obligations is primarily its capacity to violate those rights. For this primary establishment it is irrelevant what is the entity's character (public or private), size, sphere of activity and/ or ownership structure.²⁸ However, corporate size and industry sector may and do influence the *extent of* such capacity to harm. Therefore, binding transnational corporations (hereafter "TNCs") by human rights is needed in view of the power and influence that these entities have on lives of people all over the globe. In the age of globalization and TNCs, single states are no longer the only or the most powerful actors.²⁹ Corporate power is not limited to the economic sphere. Corporations increasingly operate in positions of political power and de facto authority³⁰, consolidating and instrumentalizing such power to steer political processes and ensure business-friendly policies easing their "regulatory burden".³¹ States may also be put under pressure by powerful corporate agents when underta-

²⁵ The German Federal Constitutional Court established such indirect horizontal effect for the first time in 1958 in the case *Lüth*, BVerfG, judgment of 15 January 1958, 1 BvR 400/51. For discussion, see C.D. Classen, "Die Drittwirkung der Grundrechte in der Rechtsprechung des Bundesverfassungsgerichts", *Archiv des öffentlichen Rechts* 122(1), 1997, p. 65; C.-W. Canaris, "Grundrechte und Privatrecht," *Archiv für die civilistische Praxis* 1984, 184. Bd., H. 3, 1984, p. 201.

²⁶ This is the rationale for state's duty to regulate corporate activity under the broader duty to protect.

²⁷ Cf. C.D. Classen, *supra* note 18, p. 266, 273-74; C.D. Classen, "Gesetzesvorbehalt und Dritte Gewalt: Zur demokratischen Legitimation der Rechtsprechung", *JuristenZeitung*, 58. Jahrg., Nr. 14, 2003, p. 693, at p. 701.

²⁸ Assumption in line with the UNGPs' logic.

²⁹ Multilateralism in an Era of Global Oligarchy. How Extreme Inequality Undermines International Cooperation, Oxfam Media Briefing, 23 September 2024; Krajewski, *supra* note 24, p. 3.

³⁰ Wettstein, *supra* note 5, p. 108, 134.

³¹ *Ibid.*; OHCHR, Report on corporate political engagement and responsible business conduct, 22 July 2022, A/77/201.

king to protect human rights.³² Against this backdrop, an argument opposing direct human rights obligations for corporations on grounds that, as members of society, they should enjoy equal status to individuals³³ is easily rebuttable. Inequalities in private sector are endemic³⁴ and it is exactly the power asymmetry between corporate agents and individuals that creates an enabling environment for the former to violate human rights.

The corporate capacity to harm is further fostered by corporations operating largely outside the law system, despite their being legal constructs. One manifestation of that is corporate self-regulation, which in essence boils down to business actors determining the standards they are subject to as well as remaining in control of the compliance monitoring system.³⁵ Human rights hazards are also inherent in current economic models that allow corporations to maximize profit at the expense of the rights of other members of society.³⁶ Since corporations benefit from protection of their economic interests both under international economic law³⁷ and national constitutions³⁸, the rule of law and legal consistency principles require to ensure that they themselves do not abuse human rights of others.³⁹ Or, differently put, the enjoyment of rights requires accepting and respecting the obligations arising from them. For one thing, “[n]o person, natural or legal, should be placed above the law or be allowed to operate outside of the rule of law”.⁴⁰ Secondly, the absence of corporate accountability would in many circumstances leave victims unprotected.⁴¹ As rightly pointed out in literature, state obligations

³² E.g. *Chevron Corporation and Texaco Petroleum Corporation v Ecuador*, PCA Case No. 2009-23. The company seeks orders from the arbitration tribunal that would directly contest a judgment of Ecuadorian judiciary awarding victims financial compensation for environmental harm caused by the company. See International Institute for Sustainable Development (ISID): Case Note: How Chevron v. Ecuador is Pushing the Boundaries of Arbitral Authority, <<https://www.iisd.org/itn/en/2012/04/13/case-note-how-chevron-v-ecuador-is-pushing-the-boundaries-of-arbitral-authority/>> last accessed 6 April 2025.

³³ N. Hsieh, “Should Business Have Human Rights Obligations?” *Journal of Human Rights* 14, 2015, p. 218. Hsieh’s egalitarianism concept making a corporation a subject of rights vis-a-vis an individual, but not respective obligations, fully ignores power asymmetry of such a relationship.

³⁴ E.g. Chirwa and Amodu, *supra* note 11, p. 27.

³⁵ Bilchitz, *supra* note 6, p. 42.

³⁶ Deva, *supra* note 3, p. 150. Cf. also B. Sjøfjell, “How Company Law has Failed Human Rights – and What to Do About It”, *Business and Human Rights Journal* 5, 2020, p. 179.

³⁷ A good example are Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs) under which corporate investors enjoy protection.

³⁸ In many constitutional orders, granting property rights and other economic freedoms to legal persons is seen as a logical extension of the protection given to natural persons and ‘the very fabric of [a] democratic State’. *First National Bank of SA*, *supra* note 22, paragraph 45. I Jędrzejowska-Schiffauer, “Right to Property”, *Max Planck Encyclopedia of Comparative Constitutional Law*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2024 paragraphs 10, 57. Constitutional protection of economic interests and freedoms extends to business activity undertaken in other countries. C.D. Classen, “Nationale Organisationen im Ausland?”, in J. Isensee and Paul Kirchhof (eds) *Handbuch des Staatsrechts der Bundesrepublik Deutschland*, Band X, 3rd edition, Heidelberg, C.F. Müller, 2012, p. 641, at p. 660.

³⁹ N. Carrillo-Santarelli, “Corporate Human Rights Obligations: Controversial but Necessary” (24 August 2015), <<https://www.business-humanrights.org/en/blog/corporate-human-rights-obligations-controversial-but-necessary/#one>> last accessed 6 April 2025.

⁴⁰ *New TV Karma Mohamed Tashin Al Khayat* Decision on Interlocutory Appeal Concerning Personal Jurisdiction in Contempt proceedings, STL-14-05/PT/AP/AR126.1, 2 October 2014, paragraph 84.

⁴¹ Carrillo-Santarelli, *supra* note 39.

may be insufficient because “corporate abuses neither automatically nor always engage state responsibility.”⁴² Skepticism is notably voiced as to human rights responsibility of home states for activities of their corporations in other (host) states,⁴³ especially if such responsibility should go beyond state duty to regulate third party activities. Therefore, effective protection of human rights requires that all potential perpetrators, notably powerful TNCs, have direct human rights obligations.

B. THE SPECIAL CASE OF THE RIGHT TO WATER

Water may mean different things to different people. Geography, culture and socio-economic background condition human attitudes to water. Such attitudes may be substantially different and even in tension to one another. The present analysis focuses on a nexus between business actors and human rights law approaches to water. For the former water is basically a commodity that can be marketed in one form or the other,⁴⁴ for the latter an essential element for ensuring any individual’s healthy⁴⁵ and dignified existence.⁴⁶ These incongruent perspectives stem from placing the utmost value to different aspects of water. By way of example, for businesses dealing e.g. with drinking water supply, it may be a maximum economic profit that may be gained on water’s particular unit,⁴⁷ for an individual, in turn, the quality of water that they consume, as it directly affects their health and well-being.

A real paradox is that law, instead of moderating such tensions, at times aggravates them by protecting the interests of more powerful agents. A perfect example is investment law and how it tends to undermine state capacity to ensure access to water and sanitation. Many cases of investor-state arbitration concern situations where water and sanitation supply was privatized and the concession granted to an investor. The privatization process leads to the increases in water prices, which mainly affects the poorest population.⁴⁸ One of the cases of this kind which attracted broad public attention was *Aguas del Tunari v. Bolivia*.⁴⁹ Following privatiza-

⁴² Idid. Cf. also Bilchitz, *supra* note 6, p. 6.

⁴³ Classen, *supra* note 38, p. 659.

⁴⁴ Statement by Mr. Pedro Arrojo Agudo, Special Rapporteur on the human rights to safe drinking water and sanitation at the 76th session of the United Nations General Assembly on 20 October 2021: “The commodification of water leads to its valuation as a simple economic good, under the market logic, marginalizing non-productive values, the public interest, the public trust and essential priorities such as the sustainability of ecosystems, the life and dignity of people and, therefore, human rights. In most cases, although water remains formally public, water trading markets buy and sell concessions for use, de facto favouring a progressive private appropriation of water.”

⁴⁵ Access to safe and potable water and adequate sanitation is an underlying determinant of health. CESCR General Comment No. 14 on the right to health (2000).

⁴⁶ CESCR General Comment No 15, *supra* note 2.

⁴⁷ This may have adverse consequence for the quality of water, see CESCR, ‘General Comment No 24’ (2017) on State obligations under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights in the context of business activities, August 10, 2017, paragraph 22.

⁴⁸ F. Balcerzak, *Investor-State Arbitration and Human Rights*, Leiden and Boston, Brill 2017, p. 36.

⁴⁹ *Aguas del Tunari, S.A. v. Bolivia*, International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID) Case No. ARB/02/3, October 21, 2005.

tion of water system of Cochabamba, third largest city in the country, water prices soared and many citizens were at risk of losing access to water.⁵⁰ A series of demonstrations over water rights took place between December 1999 and April 2000,⁵¹ known as Cochabamba water wars due to violent attempts to suppress the protests by the police. The government finally bowed to pressure from protesters, the water concession agreement with Aguas del Tunari was terminated and water industry re-nationalised. The company attempted a claim of US\$50 million in compensation for the loss of their investment and future profits in Bolivia, but the case was settled, allegedly as a result of international citizen pressure.⁵²

Another noteworthy example concerns the case of *Urbaser v. Argentina*⁵³, where the tribunal acknowledged that if investor companies are entitled to invoke rights resulting from international law, it may not be argued that they could not be subject to international law obligations.⁵⁴ The tribunal did not share the company's view that "guaranteeing the human right to water is a duty that may be born solely by the State, and never borne also by private companies."⁵⁵ It rightly held that in order to ensure that everyone enjoys the right to a standard of living adequate for their health and well-being, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social service,⁵⁶ "it must necessarily also be ensured that no other individual or entity, public or private, may act in disregard of such rights, which then implies a corresponding obligation, as stated in Article 30 of the Declaration [Universal Declaration of Human Rights - aut.]: 'Nothing in this Declaration may be interpreted as implying for any State, group or person any right to engage in any activity or to perform any act aimed at the destruction of any of the rights and freedoms set forth herein.'"⁵⁷ In the light of the foregoing, the tribunal's establishment that the extant IHRL does not recognize positive obligations of corporations in relation to the right to water and sanitation⁵⁸ is therefore both surprising and partly contradictory to its earlier dictum.⁵⁹ It is especially problematic for contexts where private actors are involved in the provision of water and sanitation services and where the effective

⁵⁰ Water bills charges are said to have increased by over 200-300% for some consumers before any investment was made by the company to improve the infrastructure. *Ibid.* p. 37, See also PBS: Bolivia - Leasing the Rain, June 2022, <<http://www.pbs.org/frontlineworld/stories/bolivia/timeline.html>> last accessed 6 April 2025.

⁵¹ PBS: Bolivia - Leasing the Rain, *supra* note 50, provides detailed timeline for Cochabamba events.

⁵² F. Balcerzak, *supra* note 48, p. 37.

⁵³ *Urbaser v. Argentina*, ICSID Case No. ARB/07/26.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, paragraphs 1194-95. The tribunal held that a bilateral international treaty (BIT) must be interpreted "in harmony with other rules of international law of which it forms part, including those relating to human rights."

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*, paragraph 1193.

⁵⁶ Art. 21(2) of the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

⁵⁷ *Urbaser v. Argentina*, *supra* note 53, paragraph 1197. Similar provisions feature Article 5(1) of the 1966 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and of the 1966 International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights.

⁵⁸ *Urbaser v. Argentina*, *supra* note 53, paragraph 1207. Such obligations of corporations can at a minimum be assumed under customary IHRL. S. Deva, *Treating human rights lightly: a critique of the consensus rhetoric and the language employed by the Guiding Principles*, *op.cit.*, p. 94.

⁵⁹ Chirwa and Amodu, *supra* note 11, p. 36.

realization of the right to water is dependent on the cooperation of both the state and the private partner.⁶⁰

Conflicting interests of business and local communities over water may also be observed in other contexts. Most notably, for a factory a natural water reservoir such as a river or lake may be a desired dump site where production waste waters can be discharged, lawfully or not,⁶¹ whereas whole local populations may depend on such water reservoirs for drinking water and their livelihoods⁶² or simply wish to enjoy their right to safe, clean and healthy environment.⁶³

The example of water is not isolated, but rather emblematic of a general root cause of business reluctance to respect human rights. The practice of commodifying any means and/ or factor of production⁶⁴ has an immediate consequence on how natural and human element of production is spoken of (*resources*) and treated. It also explains the corporate practice of internalizing only profits, while externalizing the costs of production on society and ecosystems.⁶⁵

As aptly put by the UN Special Rapporteur on the right to a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment, “water is the lifeblood of human beings, and life on Earth. Humans are 70 per cent water, and our brains 85 per cent.”⁶⁶ While companies are increasingly becoming aware of the risks posed by water scarcity, the main axis of this recognition is the financial impact to their own businesses.⁶⁷ Given that corporate actors in some industries are both major water consumers and polluters, ensuring access to safe and sufficient water in times of fresh water scarcity is impossible without these actors fulfilling their respective obligations. As the following section will argue, business operators already have obligations relating to the

⁶⁰ *Ibid.* The realization of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (including Goal 6 - clean water and sanitation) presupposes public-private partnerships.

⁶¹ The cases may range from irregularities in environmental impact assessment and concession granting process (see *infra* note) to company lack of compliance with environmental standards. E.g. following the ecological disaster of the Oder River in 2022, it was revealed that the Polish waters authority responsible for issuing permits for enterprises to discharge waste water into the river does not monitor the chemical state of waters, and thus the aggregate impact that such discharges have on the river ecosystems. Moreover, at least 282 illegal outlets were discovered: <https://www.euractiv.com/section/politics/short_news/polish-parliamentary-inspection-of-oder-river-reveals-illegal-wastewater-discharge/> last accessed 6 April 2025.

⁶² E.g. the case of the Guapinol River and the local community in northern Honduras whose livelihoods were put at risk when an extractive company started operating in the Botaderos National Park. OHCHR, Honduras passes historic law to protect the environment, <<https://www.ohchr.org/en/stories/2024/08/honduras-passes-historic-law-protect-environment>> last accessed 6 April 2025.

⁶³ Most recently, safe and sufficient water has been considered as one of the substantive components of the right to a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment. UN HRC, Human rights and the global water crisis, *supra* note 4.

⁶⁴ Sjäffjell, *supra* note 36, p. 180, with reference to Karl Polanyi’s conception of land (nature), labour and money as commodities.

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 182-183.

⁶⁶ UN HRC, Human rights and the global water crisis: water pollution, water scarcity and water-related disasters. Report of the Special Rapporteur on the issue of human rights obligations relating to the enjoyment of a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment, 19 January 2021, A/HRC/46/28.

⁶⁷ The Value of Water for Business, <<https://unglobalcompact.org/academy/the-value-of-water-for-business>> last accessed 6 April 2025.

right to water, and, where such obligations are wanting, they should be established. Prospectively, this may mean rethinking or even giving up certain unsustainable production models through regulatory and policy choices.

III. What corporate obligations in respect of the right to water?

The right to water is considered to fall within the guarantees of the right to an adequate standard of living under Article 11(1) of the 1966 International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (hereafter “ICESCR”).⁶⁸ The normative content of the right was concretized by the CESCR in 2002.⁶⁹ The Committee holds that the elements of the right must be adequate for human life, health and dignity⁷⁰ and interprets them as entitlements to “sufficient, safe, acceptable, physically accessible and affordable water for personal and domestic uses”.⁷¹ In essence, the *adequacy* of water presupposes the accessibility of water of sufficient quantity and quality. The Committee points to three further dimensions of water accessibility: physical, economic (affordability) and equal (non-discriminatory) access to adequate water facilities and services.⁷² The right to water thus includes the right to become and maintain access to existing water supplies and the freedom from interferences with those rights, including the freedom from arbitrary disconnections.⁷³ The CESCR indirectly also specifies certain limitations to the enjoyment of the right by individuals, as well as to the manner in which the responsible duty bearer(s) implement the right to water, namely, it must be “sustainable, ensuring that the right can be realised for present and future generations”.⁷⁴

It is arguable that, if the specific water rights are to be effectively implemented⁷⁵, any individual or entity that is capable of infringing on those rights must respect the minimum (core) standards protected by those rights. Under the ICESCR, states bear the main responsibility for the progressive realization of the water rights. However, the letter of Article 5(1) of the Covenant clearly puts limitations to acts or activities of all other non-state actors⁷⁶ (“any ... group or person”) to the extent that such acts or activities could aim at the destruction or unlawful limitation of the rights recognized in the Covenant. From that perspective, any exces-

⁶⁸ The cited provision provides for the right of everyone to an adequate standard of living, “including adequate food, clothing and housing”, where the word “including” is said to suggest an open catalogue of rights.

⁶⁹ CESCR, ‘General Comment No 15, *supra* note 2.

⁷⁰ *Ibid*, paragraph 11.

⁷¹ *Ibid*, paragraph 2.

⁷² *Ibid*, paragraph 12.

⁷³ *Ibid.*, paragraph 10.

⁷⁴ *Ibid*, paragraph 11.

⁷⁵ The need for effective human rights protection is repeatedly raised by the ECtHR which holds that the object and purpose of the Convention, as an instrument for the protection of human rights, requires that its provisions must be interpreted and applied such as to guarantee rights that are practical and effective, not theoretical and illusory; see e.g. *H.F. and Others/France* judgment of 14 September 2022 (Appl. nos. 24384/19 and 44234/20).

⁷⁶ Z. Kędzia and A. Hernandez-Polczyńska (eds), *Międzynarodowy Pakt Praw Gospodarczych, Socjalnych i Kulturalnych*, Warszawa, C.H. Beck, 2018, p. 224.

sive exploitation of limited water resources and pollution of fresh water reservoirs by business actors may be considered as potentially fulfilling the thresholds laid down in Article 5(1) for a destruction or a more excessive limitation of the right to water than is allowed under the Covenant. For such an establishment, a court may need to consider the gravity of infringements resulting from a corporate act or activity to the rights-holders. By way of example, where corporate activity results in fresh water pollution which destroys livelihoods of dependent local communities (as allegedly demonstrated in the *Chevron* case⁷⁷), the threshold for deprivation of the right to water under the cited provision is clearly met. Likewise, in the case of *Aguas del Tunari v. Bolivia*, doubling or tripling water bills by the water distribution company effectively deprived the poorest population of access to water.

While Article 5(1) ICESCR places limitations to any interference with the right to water and thus may invoke the *duty to respect*, depending on circumstances, business actors' duties may be more far-reaching. Most notably, when water services are provided by private entities on the basis of a granted concession, as was the case with *Aguas del Tunari* and Urbaser, it cannot be argued that the respective states had retained all their duties related to the water services provisions, whereas the concessionaires were free from any such duties. The duties in question are "inseparably tied to water services provision"⁷⁸, which has the consequence that, by virtue of the concession, the obligation to provide adequate water services as required under the ICESCR is taken over by the concessionaire.⁷⁹ It does not mean that the state is thus freed from all its obligations relating to the water rights; at a minimum it must monitor whether the private entity is duly fulfilling the obligations linked to the provision of water services which it voluntarily and knowingly accepted by way of a concession agreement and, if need be, ensure compliance. Clear and explicit concession provisions on allocation of specific duties may help avoid unnecessary contentions. At the same time, private actors that decide to base their business model on the provision of water services take up a public function, with all its consequences, including certain constraints on autonomously deciding when and on what conditions they cease the provision of services⁸⁰ or their operations.

⁷⁷ *Chevron v. Ecuador*, *supra* note 32.

⁷⁸ Chirwa and Amodu, *supra* note 11, p. 37.

⁷⁹ *Ibid*, 38.

⁸⁰ E.g. in Belgium all regional regulation endorses the idea of water as a public good with strong social dimension. As a consequence, in case of insolvency, individuals enjoy protection from arbitrary disconnections. C. Armeni, "The right to water in Belgium", IELRC Briefing Paper 2008-02, p. 1, at p. 3-4.

The case of the provision of water services illustrates that the allocation of concrete substantive obligations on business actors does not flow from their public or private character⁸¹, but rather the functions that such business entities have in the society⁸² and their respective capacity to infringe on concrete rights. The well-established constitutional jurisprudence acknowledges “the possibility of private persons being burdened similarly or to exactly the same degree through the indirect application of the fundamental rights, irrespective of their own fundamental rights, in particular if they come to acquire in practice comparable positions as duty holders or guarantors as the state.”⁸³ Thus, any dogmatic attempts to a priori exclude or limit private actors’ obligations to negative duties (duties to respect) only without taking account of concrete circumstances in which such an entity operates, have no legally sound footing. On the contrary, companies may need to practice all three types of duties (*respect, protect and fulfil*⁸⁴), even if they partly vary in nature and extent from State duties.⁸⁵ By the same token, the formal distinction made by the arbitration tribunal in *Urbaser* between obligations of compliance and obligations of performance (the latter, in view of the tribunal, not being attributable to any company providing the contractually required service) is contradicting national constitutional jurisprudence.⁸⁶ As aptly argued by Chirwa and Amodu, “[o]bligations of compliance can be positive in nature and hence require positive action. For example, a corporation involved in waste production might need to spend significant amounts of money to ensure that it does not pollute the environment and, hence, not violate the right to clean water, the right to food, or the right to health. To comply with such a duty, the corporation might also need to employ qualified personnel or train its existing staff. Furthermore, a human rights impact assessment might be necessary for a corporation to take steps to prevent violations of the duty to respect ESC [economic, social and cultural] rights.”⁸⁷

To sum up, privatization of water services does not mean that their provision is subject to the primacy of private gain.⁸⁸ Private providers regularly benefit economically from the stability of demand for this essential good, with this benefit being offset by positive collateral duties incumbent on them under the law as suppliers. As to the general duty to respect the right to

⁸¹ E.g. the German Federal Constitutional Court considers the distinction relevant only with regard to the establishment whether a business entity is directly or indirectly bound by the fundamental rights. The Court attributes direct binding force of the fundamental rights to publicly controlled enterprises. Concomitantly, the Court holds that the direct vs indirect division has no bearing on how far-reaching obligations may be attributed to a concrete business actor, establishing that “[d]epending on the content of the guarantee and the circumstances of the case, the indirect binding force of the fundamental rights on private persons may instead come closer to or even be the same as the binding force of the fundamental rights on the state. This is relevant (...) in particular when private enterprises themselves (...) assume functions which were previously allocated to the state as part of its services of general interest”. *BVerfG*, Judgment of the First Senate of February 22, 2011, 1 BvR 699/06, paragraph 59, English version available at: <https://www.bundesverfassungsgericht.de/SharedDocs/Entscheidungen/EN/2011/02/rs20110222_1bvr069906en.html> (25.09.2024).

⁸² *Ibid.*

⁸³ *Ibid.*, paragraph 56.

⁸⁴ See *supra* note 23.

⁸⁵ Cf. Deva, *supra* note 11, p. 95.

⁸⁶ E.g. *BVerfG*, *supra* note 81.

⁸⁷ Chirwa and Amodu, *supra* note 11, p. 36.

⁸⁸ Wettstein, *supra* note 5, p.139

water, it extends to business entities operating beyond the water services industry. This norm has been confirmed, at least for the majority of European states, by the adoption of the EU CSDDD.⁸⁹ The following section will substantiate this argument.

IV. The mode of implementing corporate obligations in respect of the right to water

The indirect model of implementing corporate human rights obligations rests primarily on regulating third party activity by a competent legislative body. Since implementing such obligations for business entities limits their own economic rights and freedoms⁹⁰, the limitation in question must fulfill certain proportionality criteria, namely pursue a legitimate purpose, be necessary in a democratic society, i.e. constitute the least restrictive means of achieving the pursued purpose and offer the benefit that outweighs the harm caused by the infringement of rights.⁹¹ The protection of human rights clearly pursues a legitimate purpose, and laws imposing constraints on business activity, insofar as it may infringe on fundamental rights of others, should provide for proportionally balancing the interests of business entities and individuals.

Globally, and most notably in Europe, the conviction that a better balancing of such potentially conflicting interests is necessary has led to the adoption of corporate human rights and environmental due diligence laws. National legislation was enacted in France (2017), Germany, Norway and Switzerland (2021). At EU level, following sectorial legislation relating to trade in timber⁹² and conflict minerals⁹³, the recently adopted CSDDD (2024) introduces general human rights and environmental due diligence obligations for large companies operating on the EU internal market. The due diligence obligations in question are process-oriented, i.e. they require companies to undertake appropriate measures to identify, assess, prevent and mitigate potential adverse impacts on people and the environment which are caused or linked to their own activity and that of their controlled entities and/ or business partners. Where actual impacts have already occurred, companies must bring them to an end and minimise their extent (Article 5(1)(b)(c)). In literature it has been argued that neither CSDDD nor national due diligence laws impose direct human rights obligations on companies.⁹⁴ Still, burdening companies with procedural duties may only be justified when those entities are concomitantly subject to substantive obligations, regardless of whether the latter are explicitly spelled out in due diligence laws or not. The CSDDD chose a technique of indirect reference to substantive duties by invoking universal human rights and environmental instruments and concrete stan-

⁸⁹ See *supra* note 8.

⁹⁰ See *supra* note 38.

⁹¹ On proportionality test in constitutional adjudication, see I. Porat, *Proportionality*, *Max Planck Encyclopedia of Comparative Constitutional Law*, Oxford, Oxford University, 2024, paragraph 4 *et seq.*

⁹² Regulation (EU) No 995/2010 of 20 October 2010 laying down the obligations of operators who place timber and timber products on the market [2010] OJ L 295/23.

⁹³ Regulation (EU) 2017/821 of 17 May 2017 laying down supply chain due diligence obligations for Union importers of tin, tantalum and tungsten, their ores, and gold originating from conflict-affected and high-risk areas [2017] OJ L 130/1.

⁹⁴ Krajewski, *supra* note 24, p. 10 *et seq.*

dards established under these instruments. Thus the CSDDD (Annex Part I-1) embraces the respect of the right to water by making reference to:

- the prohibition to restrict workers' access to adequate water and sanitation in the workplace, interpreted in line with Article 11 of the ICESCR,⁹⁵ and
- the prohibition to cause any *measurable environmental degradation*, including harmful water pollution, excessive water consumption or other impact on natural resources, that:
 - (a) *substantially impairs the natural bases for the preservation and production of food;*
 - (b) *denies a person access to safe and clean drinking water;*
 - (c) *makes it difficult for a person to access sanitary facilities or destroys them;*
 - (d) *harms a person's health, safety, normal use of land or lawfully acquired possessions;*
 - (e) *substantially adversely affects ecosystem services through which an ecosystem contributes directly or indirectly to human wellbeing;*

interpreted in line with Article 6(1) of the ICCPR and Articles 11 and 12 of the ICESCR⁹⁶. In cases of dispute, the thresholds for what constitutes a *measurable* environmental degradation, *excessive* water consumption or *substantial* impairment will need to be specified by courts. The above cited prohibitions, duly transposed by equivalent provisions of EU member states' domestic law, should be read in connection with the right of individuals, groupings and communities to lands and resources, including waters, and the right not to be deprived of means of subsistence, be it by unlawful evictions or takings of land, forests and waters, or less direct infringements on the water rights of individuals and communities resulting e.g. from mining and deforestation.⁹⁷ Also these rights, as indicated by the letter of the CSDDD, shall be interpreted in line with Articles 1 and 27 of the ICCPR and Articles 1, 2 and 11 of the ICESCR.⁹⁸

According to the letter of the Directive, the due diligence requirements should also “contribute to preserving and restoring biodiversity and improving the state of the environment, in particular the air, water and soil”.⁹⁹ Apart from the prohibition to pollute waters, the environmental due diligence relevant for the right to water encompasses the obligation to avoid or minimise adverse impacts on wetlands and their habitats.¹⁰⁰ While the purpose of environmental due diligence is said not to be limited to a better protection of human rights¹⁰¹, the focus on the latter clearly prevails from the reading of the text. Arguably, this anthropocentric perspective neither gives due credit to the intrinsic value of nature and its ecosystems, nor is it

⁹⁵ Annex to the CSDDD, Part I-1, paragraph 7.

⁹⁶ *Ibid*, paragraph 15.

⁹⁷ *Ibid*, paragraph 16. Cf. in that regard notably CESCR, ‘General comment No 26’ (2022) on land and economic, social and cultural rights, UN Document E/C.12/GC/26, i.a. paragraphs 8 and 42, the latter paragraph specifying extraterritorial obligations of home states relating to activity of corporate actors they can regulate in third (host) states.

⁹⁸ *Ibid*.

⁹⁹ CSDDD, recital 32.

¹⁰⁰ Annex to the CSDDD, Part II, paragraph 14.

¹⁰¹ Recital 32 applies the word “including” to better protect human rights, which suggests there are other aims pursued by environmental due diligence.

sufficient to contribute to the gradual change of the general mindset that treats water as a marketable economic good.¹⁰²

Overall, implementing corporate obligations in respect of the right to water through due diligence laws offers both benefits and tradeoffs. Due diligence obligations, be it for state or private entities, are normally interpreted as obligations of means, i.e. they require reasonable conduct aimed at preventing harm rather than guaranteeing that such a harm will not occur in the first place. E.g. Article 3(2) of the 2021 UN Draft Treaty on BHR stipulates that corporate due diligence obligations are to be “commensurate with their size, sector, operational context or the severity of impacts on human rights.”¹⁰³ The proportionality principle that due diligence obligations are based on thus enables to balance the interests of the duty bearer vis-à-vis that of the right holder. However, such due diligence, when interpreted in isolation from the substantive obligations whose fulfillment the procedural duties are to serve¹⁰⁴, may fall short of its own objectives. An effective enforcement of the new corporate due diligence obligations by administrative and judicial bodies will therefore depend on their readiness to assess the fulfillment of such obligations by confronting the appropriateness of the measures applied by a company with the result they were to achieve, i.e. preventing and/ or mitigating the infringement on the right to water.

A relevant question going beyond the scope of this paper is whether, and if yes, to what extent the establishment that a given company is subject to due diligence obligations in respect of the right to water will impact the future awards of arbitration tribunals in cases involving corporate infringement on individual or group interests linked to that right. Since the preparedness of arbitration tribunals to take account of such corporate due diligence obligations may not be taken for granted, the inclusion of human rights provisions within BITs¹⁰⁵ would provide useful clarification for the realisation of the right to water.¹⁰⁶

I. Conclusions

Water is a precondition for life, health and well-being of all living organisms, including humans. The right to water thus offers a strong case for the collateral obligations of business in respect of that right. Postulating such obligations requires justification and sound legal basis. By invoking fundamental principles of the rule of law and legal consistency, this paper has developed a line of interpreting extant human rights instruments as acknowledging direct

¹⁰² This transpires i.a. from conceiving of ecosystem *services* as a means to contribute, directly or indirectly, to human wellbeing. Annex to the CSDDD, Part I-1, paragraph 15.

¹⁰³ “Legally Binding Instrument to Regulate, in International Human Rights Law, the Activities of Transnational Corporations and Other Business Enterprises,” OEIGWG, 17 August 2021, <<https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/LBI3rdDRAFT.pdf>> last accessed 6 April 2025.

¹⁰⁴ Procedural obligations are both independent and an element of the substantive harm prevention rule. J. Brunnée, ‘Procedure and Substance in International Environmental Law’, in: *Collected Courses of the Hague Academy of International Law*, Brill On-line, Volume 405, 2021, p. 79, p. 99-101.

¹⁰⁵ See *supra* note 37.

¹⁰⁶ W. Schreiber, “Realizing the Right to Water in International Investment Law: An Interdisciplinary Approach to BIT Obligations”, *Natural Resources Journal* 48(2), 2008, p. 431, p. 431.

obligations of business attached to the right to water, even though such instruments do not explicitly spell out such obligations. This has direct implications for the manner in which newly established corporate sustainability due diligence obligations, including in respect of the right to water, should be implemented and enforced. While the instrument of due diligence limits corporate duties to what may reasonably be expected of a circumspect business actor given its concrete circumstances and operational context¹⁰⁷, the adequacy of measures undertaken by business must be weighed against the substantive norm of harm prevention and mitigation. Thus applied due diligence has the potential to better balance the interests of right-holders against those of powerful corporate actors, and so to contribute to a better realisation of the right to water.

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¹⁰⁷ I. Jędrzejowska-Schiffauer, “Business Responsibility for Human Rights Impact under the UN Guiding Principles: at Odds with European Union Law?” *European Law Review* 46, 2021, p. 481.